

SAR-Aware Beamforming Optimization in Active IRS-aided MISO Broadcasting for SWIPT

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Abstract—This paper considers a multiple-input single-output (MISO) broadcasting system for simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT), wherein an active intelligent reflecting surface (IRS) assists the access point (AP) in wireless information/power transfer to the physically separated information/energy receivers (IR/ER). We aim at jointly optimizing the transmit and reflect beamforming (TB/RB) weights, such that the weighted sum power at the ERs is maximized subject to the quality-of-service requirements of the IRs, the transmit sum-power constraints of the AP and the IRS, and the specific absorption rate (SAR) restrictions imposed on the former. We develop an alternating optimization algorithm that makes use of the semi-definite relaxation (SDR) method to efficiently tackle this challenging non-convex optimization problem. We prove that no energy beams are required and derive the SDR tightness condition of the TB optimization sub-problem. Numerical simulations demonstrate the superior performance of the active IRS over its passive counterpart, unveil the performance gains of the proposed design over baseline schemes, and provide valuable insights.

Index Terms—Active intelligent reflecting surface (IRS), simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT), multiple-input single-output (MISO) broadcasting, specific absorption rate (SAR), optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of the novel intelligent reflecting surface (IRS) technology as a means to boost the performance of simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) systems has been studied manifold in the literature, thanks to its ability to dynamically reconfigure the wireless channel [1]. These works consider a *passive* IRS implementation, where one can jointly adjust the phase shifts induced by the reflecting elements (RE) to the incident radio-frequency (RF) signal to *reflect* the latter in a controllable manner [2]–[5]. On the downside, this IRS type requires a large number of REs, which is translated into considerable cost and energy consumption [6], to effectively compensate for the detrimental effect of the double path loss over the IRS-cascaded access point (AP)–user channels on the efficiency of energy transfer.

An *active* IRS variant, wherein each RE is able to both *amplify* and reflect the incident RF signal with the aid of an active load (negative resistance) such as a tunnel diode, has recently emerged in response to this issue. The studies [7]–[9] investigate relevant designs for maximizing the data rate of single-input single-/multiple-output (SISO/SIMO) links, whereas [10]

focuses on the joint optimization of the transmit/reflect beamforming (TB/RB) weights at the AP/IRS to minimize the AP’s transmit sum-power (TSP) in a multiple-input single-output (MISO) broadcasting system. The latter problem is revisited in [11], assuming a corresponding SWIPT setup. These works indicated that active IRS technology substantially outperforms its passive counterpart or, conversely, undercuts the cost and energy consumption required to achieve a target performance, provided that the number of REs is relatively small and the power consumption budget is moderate.

However, given the short separation distance between the AP and the energy receivers (ER), TB design should also comply in practice with specific absorption rate (SAR) limitations¹, which refer to the maximum allowable level of absorbed RF power per unit mass of human tissue for different body parts (e.g., whole body, partial body, head, hands, etc.) [12]. Although SAR-aware designs have been proposed for SWIPT systems [13], [14], no prior study has explored the impact of SAR constraints on the design and performance of an IRS-aided SWIPT system, let alone on a respective setup with an active IRS, to the best of our knowledge.

Motivated by the above, in this paper we aim at jointly optimizing the TB/RB weights in a MISO broadcasting system with physically separated information receivers (IR) and ERs, such that the weighted sum-power (WSP) at the ERs is maximized subject to the signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR) requirements of the IRs, the TSP constraints of the AP and the IRS, and the SAR restrictions imposed on the former. We assume that the AP is linked with the users via both direct and IRS-cascaded channels to facilitate comparisons with the scenario where no IRS is deployed. We also consider availability of perfect channel state information (CSI) at the AP to focus on the behavior of the proposed strategy and obtain performance bounds, thus leaving the study of corresponding robust schemes against channel uncertainty as future work. We develop an alternating optimization (AO) algorithm that utilizes the semi-definite relaxation (SDR) method to efficiently tackle this challenging non-convex optimization problem. We prove that no energy beams are required and derive the SDR tightness condition of the TB optimization sub-problem. Numerical simulation results indicate the superiority of the active IRS over its passive counterpart, unveil the performance gains of the proposed design over baseline schemes, and provide valuable insights.

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¹RB design is not subject to SAR constraints due to the active IRS’s small maximum transmit power (around 10-30 mW), which is dictated by power consumption limitations.

Fig. 1. System setup.

Notation: $\mathbf{x}(n)$: the n -th element of the column vector \mathbf{x} ; $\mathbf{x}_{1:N}$: the first N elements of \mathbf{x} ; $\mathbf{X}(n, m)$: the (n, m) -th entry of matrix \mathbf{X} ; $\mathbf{0}_{N,1}$ and $\mathbf{0}_{1,N}$: the N -dimensional column and row, respectively, null vector; \mathbf{I}_N : the $N \times N$ identity matrix; \mathbb{C}^N : the set of complex N -dimensional vectors; $\mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$: the set of complex $N \times M$ matrices; \mathbb{H}^N : the set of Hermitian $N \times N$ matrices; $\|\cdot\|$: the Euclidean norm of \mathbf{x} ; \mathbf{X}^* , \mathbf{X}^T , \mathbf{X}^\dagger , $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{X})$, $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{X})$, $\|\mathbf{X}\|_F$: the complex conjugate, transpose, complex conjugate transpose, trace, rank, and Frobenius norm, respectively, of a matrix \mathbf{X} with appropriate size; $\text{diag}(\mathbf{x})$: a diagonal matrix with main diagonal \mathbf{x} ; $\text{Diag}(\mathbf{X})$: the main diagonal of \mathbf{X} ; $\mathbf{X} \succeq \mathbf{0}$: \mathbf{X} is positive semi-definite (PSD); $|x|$: the magnitude of the complex scalar x ; $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$: the expectation operator; $\mathcal{CN}(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $\mathcal{U}(\cdot, \cdot)$: the circularly symmetric complex Gaussian and the uniform distribution, respectively.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The considered IRS-aided SWIPT system is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of an AP with a set $\mathcal{M} \triangleq \{1, \dots, M\}$ of antennas, an active IRS with a set $\mathcal{N} \triangleq \{1, \dots, N\}$ of REs, and two sets of single-antenna receivers, namely, a set $\mathcal{K}_I \triangleq \{1, \dots, K_I\}$ of IRs and a set $\mathcal{K}_E \triangleq \{1, \dots, K_E\}$ of ERs. Throughout the paper, we address the members of these sets via the indexes $m \in \mathcal{M}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}$, $k, i \in \mathcal{K}_I$, and $l, j \in \mathcal{K}_E$.

Let $\mathbf{w}_i \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{v}_j \in \mathbb{C}^M$ denote the TB vectors assigned to IR i and ER j , respectively. The signal transmitted from the AP, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^M$, is given by

$$\mathbf{x} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i s_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j e_j, \quad (1)$$

where $s_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ and $e_j \in \mathbb{C}$, which satisfies $\mathbb{E}[|e_j|^2] = 1$, are the information-bearing and energy-carrying signals destined for IR i and ER j , respectively. Let $P_A > 0$ denote the budget on AP's TSP, $P_1 = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}^\dagger \mathbf{x}]$. Then,

$$P_1 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \|\mathbf{w}_i\|^2 + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \|\mathbf{v}_j\|^2 \leq P_A. \quad (2)$$

We assume quasi-static, frequency-flat fading channels. Let $\mathbf{h}_{d,i}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^N$ denote the baseband equivalent

channels from the AP and the IRS, respectively, to IR i . The corresponding channels for ER j are denoted by $\mathbf{g}_{d,j}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^N$, respectively, whereas $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ denotes the channel from the AP to the IRS. Let $\Theta = \text{diag}(u_1, \dots, u_N) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ be the RB matrix of the IRS, where $u_n = \alpha_n e^{j\phi_n}$ denotes the reflection coefficient of the n -th RE, $\alpha_n \geq 0$ represents its reflection amplitude, and $\phi_n \in [0, 2\pi)$ stands for its phase shift. The effective baseband equivalent channels from the AP to IR i and ER j , $\mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{g}_j^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^M$, are respectively defined as $\mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \triangleq \mathbf{h}_{d,i}^\dagger + \mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger \Theta \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{h}_{d,i}^\dagger + \theta^\dagger \mathbf{H}_i$ and $\mathbf{g}_j^\dagger \triangleq \mathbf{g}_{d,j}^\dagger + \mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \Theta \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{g}_{d,j}^\dagger + \theta^\dagger \mathbf{G}_j$, where $\theta \in \mathbb{C}^N$, $\mathbf{H}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, and $\mathbf{G}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ are defined as $\theta \triangleq \text{Diag}(\Theta^*)$, $\mathbf{H}_i \triangleq \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger) \mathbf{F}$, and $\mathbf{G}_j \triangleq \text{diag}(\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger) \mathbf{F}$, respectively.

Let $\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ denote the incident signal at the IRS, $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}$. Then, the amplified and reflected by the IRS signal, $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is expressed as $\mathbf{t} = \Theta(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{z}) = \Theta(\mathbf{F}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{z})$, where $\mathbf{z} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \delta^2 \mathbf{I}_N)$ represents the IRS's thermal noise. Let $P_I > 0$ denote the budget of the IRS's TSP, $P_2 = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{t}^\dagger \mathbf{t}]$. Then,

$$P_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \|\Theta \mathbf{F} \mathbf{w}_i\|^2 + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \|\Theta \mathbf{F} \mathbf{v}_j\|^2 + \delta^2 \|\Theta\|_F^2 \leq P_I. \quad (3)$$

The received signal at IR i , $y_i \in \mathbb{C}$, is written as $y_i = \mathbf{h}_{d,i}^\dagger \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger \mathbf{t} + n_i = \mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger \Theta \mathbf{z} + n_i$, where $n_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_i^2)$ represents the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at IR i . By assuming that the IRs are not capable of canceling the interference caused by the pseudo-random energy signals, the SINR constraint of IR i is given by

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i|^2}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus \{i\}} |\mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k|^2 + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} |\mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \mathbf{v}_j|^2 + \bar{I}_i(\Theta)} \geq \Gamma_i, \quad (4)$$

where $\Gamma_i > 0$ denotes the minimum SINR target of IR i and $\bar{I}_i(\Theta) \triangleq \delta^2 \|\mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger \Theta\|^2 + \sigma_i^2$.

Furthermore, by ignoring the negligible AWGN power, the received RF power at ER j is expressed as

$$Q_j = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} |\mathbf{g}_j^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i|^2 + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{K}_E} |\mathbf{g}_j^\dagger \mathbf{v}_l|^2 + \delta^2 \|\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \Theta\|^2. \quad (5)$$

Thus, the WSP received at the ERs is written as

$$\begin{aligned} P &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j Q_j \\ &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{S} \mathbf{w}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{S} \mathbf{v}_j + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j \delta^2 \|\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \Theta\|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{H}^M$ is defined as $\mathbf{S} \triangleq \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j \mathbf{g}_j \mathbf{g}_j^\dagger$ and $\omega_j \geq 0$ denotes the energy priority weight of ER j .

The SAR constraints of the AP are given by [15], [16]:

$$\text{SAR}_l = \mathbb{E}[\text{Tr}(\mathbf{x}^\dagger \mathbf{A}_l \mathbf{x})]$$

²Recall that: i) $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{g} \mathbf{g}^\dagger$ is a $N \times N$ PSD matrix for any arbitrary vector $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{C}^N$; and ii) the sum of PSD matrices is a PSD matrix as well.

$$= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{A}_l \mathbf{w}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{A}_l \mathbf{v}_j \leq \xi_l, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_l \in \mathbb{H}^M$ and $\xi_l > 0$ represent the SAR matrix and SAR limit, respectively, for the l -th body area of interest, $l \in \mathcal{L} \triangleq \{1, \dots, L\}$. The SAR matrices, which are commonly obtained offline during testing, describe the dependence of the SAR measurements on the transmitted signals. Consequently, they depend on antenna type, operating frequency, etc.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND PROPOSED SOLUTION

A. Problem Formulation

The optimization problem of interest is mathematically formulated as follows:

$$(P1): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}, \{\mathbf{v}_j\}, \Theta} P \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \text{SINR}_i \geq \Gamma_i, \quad (8b)$$

$$P_1 \leq P_A, \quad (8c)$$

$$P_2 \leq P_I, \quad (8d)$$

$$\text{SAR}_l \leq \xi_l. \quad (8e)$$

(P1) is a challenging non-convex optimization problem, due to the intricate coupling of the decision variables in both the objective function and the constraints. Moreover, it is unknown whether the use of dedicated energy beams is required to obtain the optimal solution of (P1) or not, due to the SAR constraints and the involvement of an active IRS.

B. Energy Beamforming: Is It Required?

Next, we apply the SDR method to study the necessity of energy beamforming. Specifically, we introduce the PSD matrix variables $\mathbf{W}_i \in \mathbb{H}^M$ and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{H}^M$, which are defined as $\mathbf{W}_i \triangleq \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger$ and $\mathbf{V} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger$ and should satisfy $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{W}_i) \leq 1$ and $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{V}) \leq \min(M, K_E)$, respectively. We also define $\mathbf{R}_i \in \mathbb{H}^M$ and $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ as $\mathbf{R}_i \triangleq \mathbf{h}_i \mathbf{h}_i^\dagger$ and $\mathbf{C} \triangleq \mathbf{F}^\dagger \Theta^\dagger \Theta \mathbf{F}$ and let $\bar{P}_I \triangleq P_I - \delta^2 \|\Theta\|_F^2$ and $\bar{\Gamma}_i \triangleq \frac{\Gamma_i}{\Gamma_i + 1}$. By relaxing the non-convex rank constraints, we obtain:

$$(P2): \max_{\mathcal{Z}} f(\mathcal{Z}) \quad (9a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \frac{\text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i)}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_k) + \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{V}) + \bar{\Gamma}_i(\Theta)} \geq \bar{\Gamma}_i, \quad (9b)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{W}_i) + \text{Tr}(\mathbf{V}) \leq P_A, \quad (9c)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{C} \mathbf{W}_i) + \text{Tr}(\mathbf{C} \mathbf{V}) \leq \bar{P}_I, \quad (9d)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{A}_l \mathbf{W}_i) + \text{Tr}(\mathbf{A}_l \mathbf{V}) \leq \xi_l, \quad (9e)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_i \succeq \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{V} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad (9f)$$

where $\mathcal{Z} \triangleq \{\{\mathbf{W}_i\}, \mathbf{V}, \Theta\}$ denotes the set of feasible solutions and

$$f(\mathcal{Z}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S} \mathbf{W}_i) + \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S} \mathbf{V}) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j \delta^2 \|\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \Theta\|_F^2. \quad (10)$$

Theorem 1. Assuming that (P2) is feasible, then there always exists an optimal solution, denoted by $\{\{\mathbf{W}_i^*\}, \mathbf{V}^*, \Theta^*\}$, satisfying $\mathbf{V}^* = \mathbf{0}$.

Proof. Please refer to Appendix A.

C. Alternating Optimization

Based on Theorem 1, we have to equivalently solve the following optimization problem:

$$(P3): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}, \Theta} h(\mathbf{w}_i, \Theta) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{S} \mathbf{w}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j \delta^2 \|\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \Theta\|_F^2 \quad (11a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \frac{|\mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i|^2}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus \{i\}} |\mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k|^2 + \delta^2 \|\mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger \Theta\|_F^2 + \sigma_i^2} \geq \Gamma_i, \quad (11b)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \|\mathbf{w}_i\|^2 \leq P_A, \quad (11c)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \|\Theta \mathbf{F} \mathbf{w}_i\|^2 + \delta^2 \|\Theta\|_F^2 \leq P_I, \quad (11d)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{A}_l \mathbf{w}_i \leq \xi_l. \quad (11e)$$

(P3) is obtained from (P1) by setting $\mathbf{v}_j = \mathbf{0}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{K}_E$. In the sequence, we develop an AO algorithm to efficiently tackle this non-convex optimization problem.

1) *Transmit Beamforming Optimization:* For fixed Θ , the optimization problem of interest takes the form:

$$(P4): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{S} \mathbf{w}_i \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \text{Eqs. (11b)–(11e)}. \quad (12b)$$

To solve (P4), we apply the SDR method. The resulting optimization problem, which we will call (P5), is obtained from (P2)', which is presented in Appendix A and is equivalent to (P2) with $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{0}$, by fixing Θ and dropping the constant term $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j \delta^2 \|\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \Theta\|_F^2$ from the objective function. (P5) corresponds to a standard semi-definite program (SDP). This convex optimization problem can be solved in polynomial time by convex optimization solvers that utilize interior-point methods, such as CVX [17].

Theorem 2. If $\mathbf{C} \succeq \mathbf{0}$, then the optimal solution of (P5), \mathbf{W}_i^* , satisfies $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{W}_i^*) = 1$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$; therefore, we can directly recover the optimal solution of (P4), \mathbf{w}_i^* , via the Cholesky decomposition $\mathbf{W}_i^* = \mathbf{w}_i^* (\mathbf{w}_i^*)^\dagger$.

Proof. Based on the partial Lagrangian and dual problem of (P5), we define:

$$\mathbf{X}_i \triangleq \mathbf{S} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \lambda_k \mathbf{R}_k - \lambda_i \tilde{\Gamma}_i \mathbf{R}_i + \mu \mathbf{I}_M + \nu \mathbf{C} + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \rho_l \mathbf{A}_l, \quad (13)$$

where $\tilde{\Gamma}_i \triangleq 1 + \frac{1}{\bar{\Gamma}_i} = \frac{1}{\bar{\Gamma}_i}$ and $\{\lambda_i, \mu, \nu, \rho_l\}$ are dual variables. Clearly, this $M \times M$ matrix is a PSD one if and only if

$\mathbf{C} \succeq \mathbf{0}$. Then, by following the steps in Appendix A of [13], we can readily show that $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{X}_i) \geq M - 1$. therefore, $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{W}_i) \leq 1$ due to the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) condition of (P5) $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{W}_i \mathbf{X}_i) = 0$. \square

In the general case, the SDR tightness condition presented in Theorem 2 does not hold. Then, we can construct a suboptimal rank-one solution via eigen-decomposition-based approximation or Gaussian randomization (GR) [18].

2) *Reflect Beamforming Optimization*: For given $\{\mathbf{w}_i\}$, (P3) is reduced to:

$$(P6): \max_{\Theta} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{S} \mathbf{w}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j \delta^2 \left\| \mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger \Theta \right\|^2 \quad (14a)$$

$$\text{s.t. Eq. (11b), Eq. (11d).} \quad (14b)$$

Let $\bar{N} \triangleq N + 1$, $a_{i,k} \triangleq \mathbf{h}_{d,i}^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k$, and $b_{j,k} \triangleq \mathbf{g}_{d,j}^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k$. We define $\bar{\theta} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N}}$ as $\bar{\theta} \triangleq [\theta^T \ 1]^T$; $\mathbf{a}_{i,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N}}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{j,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N}}$ as $\mathbf{a}_{i,k} \triangleq \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{w}_k$ and $\mathbf{b}_{j,k} \triangleq \mathbf{G}_j \mathbf{w}_k$; $\mathbf{L}_{i,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N} \times \bar{N}}$ and $\mathbf{P}_{j,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N} \times \bar{N}}$ as $\mathbf{L}_{i,k} \triangleq [\mathbf{a}_{i,k} \mathbf{a}_{i,k}^\dagger, \mathbf{a}_{i,k} a_{i,k}^*; \mathbf{a}_{i,k}^\dagger a_{i,k}, 0]$ and $\mathbf{P}_{j,k} \triangleq [\mathbf{b}_{j,k} \mathbf{b}_{j,k}^\dagger, \mathbf{b}_{j,k} b_{j,k}^*; \mathbf{b}_{j,k}^\dagger b_{j,k}, 0]$; $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N} \times \bar{N}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{T}}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N} \times \bar{N}}$ as $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_i \triangleq \text{diag}([\mathbf{h}_{r,i}^\dagger, 0]) \text{diag}([\mathbf{h}_{r,i}, 0])$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{T}}_j \triangleq \text{diag}([\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^\dagger, 0]) \text{diag}([\mathbf{g}_{r,j}, 0])$; and $\mathbf{Q}_i \in \mathbb{H}^{\bar{N}}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_i \in \mathbb{H}^{\bar{N}}$ as $\mathbf{Q}_i \triangleq \text{diag}(\mathbf{F} \mathbf{w}_i) (\text{diag}(\mathbf{F} \mathbf{w}_i))^\dagger$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_i \triangleq [\text{diag}(\text{Diag}(\mathbf{Q}_i)), \mathbf{0}_{N,1}; \mathbf{0}_{1,\bar{N}}]$, respectively³. Next, we apply the SDR method to transform (P6) into a convex SDP which can be efficiently solved by CVX, i.e., we introduce $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{H}^{\bar{N}}$, which is defined as $\mathbf{U} \triangleq \bar{\theta} \bar{\theta}^\dagger$ and should satisfy $\mathbf{U} \succeq \mathbf{0}$ and $\text{Rank}(\mathbf{U}) \leq 1$, and drop the non-convex rank constraint to obtain

$$(P7): \max_{\mathbf{U}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j g(\mathbf{U}) \quad (15a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \frac{\text{Tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{L}}_{i,i} \mathbf{U}) + |a_{i,i}|^2}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus \{i\}} (\text{Tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{L}}_{i,k} \mathbf{U}) + |a_{i,k}|^2) + \tilde{I}_i(\mathbf{U})} \geq \Gamma_i, \quad (15b)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_i \mathbf{U}) + \delta^2 \text{Tr}(\mathbf{U}) \leq P_I, \quad (15c)$$

$$\mathbf{U} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad (15d)$$

where $\tilde{I}_i \triangleq \delta^2 \text{Tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_i \mathbf{U}) + \sigma_i^2$ and

$$g(\mathbf{U}) \triangleq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} (\text{Tr}(\mathbf{P}_{j,i} \mathbf{U}) + |b_{j,i}|^2) + \delta^2 \text{Tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{T}}_j \mathbf{U}). \quad (16)$$

If the SDR is tight, we can recover $\bar{\theta}^*$ from \mathbf{U}^* as $\mathbf{U}^* = \bar{\theta}^* (\bar{\theta}^*)^\dagger$; then, $\theta^* = \bar{\theta}_{1:N}^*$. In the general case, though, we have to obtain a sub-optimal rank-one solution, e.g., via GR.

³Zero-padding of a PSD matrix results in a PSD matrix as well.

Algorithm 1 AO Algorithm for Solving Problem (P3).

- 1: Set the convergence tolerance $0 \leq \varepsilon \ll 1$, the iteration index $t = 0$, and the maximum number of iterations T_{\max} ; initialize $\Theta^{(0)}$ with $\alpha_n^{(0)} = 1$ and $\phi_n^{(0)} \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi)$, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$;
 - 2: **repeat**
 - 3: Solve (P5) with given $\Theta^{(t)}$ to obtain $\{\mathbf{w}_i^{(t+1)}\}$;
 - 4: Solve (P7) with given $\{\mathbf{w}_i^{(t+1)}\}$ to obtain $\Theta^{(t+1)}$;
 - 5: $t = t + 1$;
 - 6: **until**
 - 7: $|h_{t+1} - h_t| / |h_t| \leq \varepsilon$, where $h_t \equiv h(\mathbf{W}_i^{(t)}, \Theta^{(t)})$, or $t > T_{\max}$;
 - 8: Output: $\{\mathbf{w}_i^*\}$, Θ^* .
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3) *Convergence and Complexity Analysis*: The overall AO algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1. Its convergence is guaranteed, since the objective value of (P3), which is upper bounded, is non-decreasing over the iterations. Regarding its computational complexity, the worst-case complexity of obtaining an ε -accurate solution for an SDP with m SDP constraints that involve each an n -dimensional PSD matrix variable via an interior-point algorithm is in the order of $\mathcal{O}(\log(\frac{1}{\varepsilon}) m (n^{3.5} + mn^{2.5} + m^2))$, where $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ denotes the big-O notation [19]. Therefore, the overall complexity of the AO algorithm is in the order of

$$\mathcal{O} \left[I_{\text{iter}} \log \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \right) \left(\underbrace{C_1}_{(P5)} + \underbrace{C_2}_{(P7)} \right) \right],$$

where $C_r = m_r (n_r^{3.5} + m_r n_r^{2.5} + m_r^2)$, $r \in \{1, 2\}$, $m_1 \triangleq 2(K_I + 1) + L$, $n_1 \triangleq M$, $m_2 \triangleq K_I + 2$, and $n_2 \triangleq \bar{N}$, while I_{iter} represents the number of iterations.

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we validate the effectiveness of the proposed design via numerical simulations. Large-scale path loss is modeled as $L(d) = C_0 \left(\frac{d}{d_0}\right)^{-\zeta}$, where $C_0 = -30$ dB denotes the path loss at a reference distance of $d_0 = 1$ m, d represents the propagation distance, and ζ stands for the path loss exponent. The latter equals $\zeta_r = 2.2$ in the AP-IRS and IRS-users channels and $\zeta_d = 3$ in the AP-users links. We consider the Rician fading model with a Rician factor of $\kappa = 5$ dB for all links. Unless specified otherwise, the system parameters are set as follows: $M = 4$, $N = 50$, $K_I = K_E = 2$, $P_A = 23$ dBm, $P_I = 5$ dBm, $L = 1$, and $\xi_l = \xi = 1.6$ W/Kg. Also, $\Gamma_i = \Gamma$ dB and $\sigma_i^2 = \sigma^2 = \delta^2 = -80$ dBm, $\forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$. In addition, $\omega_j = 1$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{K}_E$. The simulation results refer to the achieved WSP obtained after 100 independent runs over the random channels and users' locations.

In Fig. 2(a), we vary the number of REs and compare the performance of the proposed scheme against the one achieved in the following scenarios: 1) The reflection amplitudes of all REs are identical (yet optimized), i.e., $\alpha_n = \alpha$, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$. 2) A passive IRS is utilized, in which case we set the AP's TSP budget to $P'_A \triangleq P_A + P_I$ to ensure a fair comparison. 3) The phase shifts of the passive IRS are randomly set. We observe that the active IRS substantially outperforms its

Fig. 2. Average WSP vs. (a) number of REs, (b) Rician factor, (c) SINR target, and (d) SAR limit.

passive counterpart. This plot also highlights the importance of optimizing the individual reflection amplitudes or phase shifts of each RE in the active or passive IRS scenario, respectively. Finally, we notice that the performance improves with the number of REs due to the higher amplification (active IRS) or coherent beamforming (passive IRS) gains, respectively.

In Fig. 2(b), we vary the Rician factor and compare the performance of the respective active- and passive-IRS-enhanced systems for different values of P_I . We note that the active IRS benefits more from the stronger line-of-sight (LOS) channel component than its passive counterpart. Furthermore, this figure shows that an increase in P_I improves significantly the performance of the active IRS-aided system, while a corresponding increase for P'_A provides only a minor benefit to the equivalent passive IRS-assisted system.

In Fig. 2(c), we vary the minimum SINR requirement of the IRs and compare the performance of the two systems assuming different values of P_A . We observe that the performance gets worse as the SINR target increases, since we have to adapt our design to meet the stringent QoS requirements of the IRs at the cost of the EH requirements of the ERs. Increasing the TSP budget of the AP benefits the performance, especially in the active IRS scenario, but not as much as one might expect, due to the SAR requirements that have to be met as well.

Finally, in Fig. 2(d) we vary the SAR limit. We notice that the performance gets worse for tighter SAR constraints, as expected. However, we also note that a higher P_I value results

in a considerable power gain as well, without the need for increasing the AP's TSP; this is particularly beneficial under the considered SAR regulations.

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the joint TB/RB design of an active IRS-aided MISO broadcasting system with physically separated IRs and ERs was optimized, in order to maximize the WSP at the ERs taking into account the SAR constraints of the AP. We proved that no energy beams are required and derived the SDR tightness condition of the developed AO algorithm's TB optimization sub-problem. Numerical simulations demonstrated the superior performance of the active IRS over its passive counterpart, unveiled the performance gains of the proposed design over baseline schemes, and provide valuable insights. In the future, we plan to extend this work by developing a corresponding robust optimal design against channel uncertainty.

APPENDIX A: PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Proof. By setting $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{0}$ in (P2), we obtain:

$$(P2)': \max_{\{\mathbf{W}_i\}, \Theta} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S}\mathbf{W}_i) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \omega_j \delta^2 \|\mathbf{g}_{r,j}^2 \Theta\|_F^2 \quad (17a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \frac{\text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i)}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_k) + \bar{I}(\Theta, \mathbf{z})} \geq \bar{\Gamma}_i, \quad (17b)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{W}_i) \leq P_A, \quad (17c)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{C}\mathbf{W}_i) \leq \bar{P}_I, \quad (17d)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_i} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{A}_I \mathbf{W}_i) \leq \xi_I, \quad (17e)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_i \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (17f)$$

We denote by E_1^* and E_2^* the optimal objective values of problems (P2) and (P2)', respectively, and by $\{\{\mathbf{W}_i^*\}, \mathbf{V}^*, \Theta^*\}$ the optimal solution of (P2). Consider the set $\mathcal{R} \triangleq \{\{\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_i\}, \Theta^*\}$, where $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_i = \mathbf{W}_i^*, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus \{q\}$, and $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_q = \mathbf{W}_q^* + \mathbf{V}^*, \forall q \in \mathcal{K}_I$. If \mathcal{R} corresponds to a feasible solution of (P2)', then it achieves an objective value E_1^* which, of course, cannot exceed the optimal objective value E_2^* of (P2)', i.e., $E_1^* \leq E_2^*$. On the other hand, we know that $E_1^* \geq E_2^*$, since (P2)' is a special case of (P2) with $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{0}$. Therefore, if we show that \mathcal{R} is a feasible solution of (P2)', we would prove that $E_1^* = E_2^*$, which suggests that we only need to solve (P2) with $\mathbf{V}^* = \mathbf{0}$ to obtain its optimal solution.

It is trivial to verify that \mathcal{R} fulfills the constraints in Eq. (17c)–Eq. (17e). Next, we show that it also fulfills the SINR constraints of (P2)'. To this end, we initially rewrite Eq. (17b) as follows:

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_k) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \bar{I}(\Theta, \mathbf{z}) \geq 0. \quad (18)$$

Likewise, we rewrite the SINR constraints of (P2) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_k) \\ & - \bar{\Gamma}_i \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{V}) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \bar{I}(\Theta, \mathbf{z}) \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Then, for any $i \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus \{q\}$, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_i) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \bar{I}(\Theta^*, \mathbf{z}) \\ & = \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus q} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_k^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_q^*) \\ & - \bar{\Gamma}_i \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{V}^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \bar{I}(\Theta^*, \mathbf{z}) \\ & = \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_k^*) \\ & - \bar{\Gamma}_i \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{V}^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \bar{I}(\Theta^*, \mathbf{z}) \stackrel{(19)}{\geq} 0. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Similarly, for any $q \in \mathcal{K}_I$, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_q \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_q) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_q \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \bar{I}(\Theta^*, \mathbf{z}) \\ & = \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_q \mathbf{W}_q^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_q \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_q \mathbf{W}_k^*) \\ & + \widehat{\Gamma}_q \mathbf{R}_q \mathbf{V}^* - \bar{\Gamma}_q \bar{I}(\Theta^*, \mathbf{z}) \\ & \geq \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_q \mathbf{W}_q^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_q \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_q \mathbf{W}_k^*) \\ & - \bar{\Gamma}_q \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_q \mathbf{V}^*) - \bar{\Gamma}_q \bar{I}(\Theta^*, \mathbf{z}) \stackrel{(19)}{\geq} 0, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $\widehat{\Gamma}_q \triangleq 1 - \bar{\Gamma}_q = \frac{1}{\bar{\Gamma}_q + 1}$. Hence, $\forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$,

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_i) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_k) - \bar{\Gamma}_i \bar{I}(\Theta, \mathbf{z}) \geq 0. \quad (22)$$

Therefore, \mathcal{R} is a feasible solution to (P2)' which achieves an objective value $E_1^* \leq E_2^*$. This concludes the proof. \square

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